

Can Bangladesh bring back the green cover through indigenous species plantation?

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Research Article

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Abstract

Per capita forestland in Bangladesh is declining at an alarming rate. The recurrent anthropogenic disturbances have rendered the natural forests inhospitable for the natural regeneration and growth of wild plant associates, causing a net loss of biodiversity. Instead of native species plantation, exotic species have become an increasingly important source of timber, which negatively impacts the natural habitats. Hence, the study explored different options for native species plantation based on habitat types and the level of degradation. It is revealed that natural succession is suitable for increasing the canopy coverage in natural forest areas. In the core and buffer zones of each forest natural regeneration should be facilitated to maintain the ecological balance and to ensure continuous forest coverage. In addition, direct seeding in the buffer zone and degraded forest areas can improve the naturalness. Advanced regeneration of rare or endangered species can protect the species from extinction. Very fast-growing and timbering native species should be planted in the encroached areas. The deep-rooted species can reinforce riverbanks against erosion better than the shallow-rooted ground cover. Trees with large canopies and deep roots can protect the coastal belt. Screw pine (*Pandanus*) can grow on dunes and has thick 'prop roots' to anchor itself in the loose sand. *Tanguya* plantation should consist of growing annual crops along with forest trees during the early establishment of forest plantations on the hills. Fast-growing and timbering trees can increase the green cover in the fallow land. The ornamental trees simultaneously can increase the green cover and beauty in urban areas.

Introduction

The incremental over-population and its forces invade the natural habitats, accelerating the demise of the natural forests (Ali et al. 2023; Hossain et al. 2023; Raihan et al. 2023; Masum et al. 2023; Hassan et al. 2023). During the past 15 years, Bangladesh lost almost 50% of its natural coverage (Rahman & Biswas 2023). Due to high population density and sharply skewed distribution of land, the forest resources are overexploited (Raihan et al. 2023; Joireman & Haddad 2023; Miah et al. 2023).

Per capita forestland in the country is around 0.02 ha (Farukh et al. 2023). The recurrent anthropogenic disturbances have rendered the natural forests inhospitable for the natural regeneration and growth of wild plant associates, causing a net loss of biodiversity (Rahman 2023a; Rahman 2009; Rahman et al. 2007; Rahman et al. 2009; Rahman & Vacik 2009, 10). It is predicted that an additional 20 per cent of the trees will be lost over the next decade. If that happens, the forest ecology will begin to simply unravel. In Bangladesh, illegal logging is more destructive than commercial logging (Rahman 2021, Rahman 2022 a, b). The land grabbers follow the roads deep into previously impenetrable forests and then destroy tracts to make it look as if they own them (Rahman et al. 2009). Encroachment of forest land, illegal logging, regeneration destruction, logging, litter sweeping, animal grazing, shifting cultivation, soil disturbances, and recreational activities like picnics are the main causes of massive erosion of the dipterocarp forests (Rahman et al. 2009; Rahman & Vacik 2009, 2010). The hydroelectricity project, ethnic conflict, encroachment, jhum cultivation, land sliding, hill cutting and illegal logging are the main factors involved in the degradation of hill forests (Farukh et al. 2023, Habib 2023). Poverty, profit-making, over-exploitation

of forest products, illegal logging, natural disaster, salinity and sedimentation cause the deforestation of coastal forests (Rahman 2022 a, b).

Different studies show that all our natural forests are critically degraded to the point where they are unable to maintain environmental sustainability (Rahman 2023 b, c). On the other hand, the cities of Bangladesh have become urban mayhem by losing living ambience. The single-storied residential buildings with open green spaces are fast disappearing and multistoried buildings are replacing them (Akteruzzaman et al. 2023; Ruszczyk et al. 2023). With disappearing natural habitats Bangladesh is losing its ecological balance. Ensuring a long-term healthy environment by using green development is a crying need for future generations. The green cover is essential for maintaining biodiversity and ensuring ecological goods and services, such as clean air, clean water, carbon sequestration, and flood control (Lukito & Rohmatiah 2013; Pitol & Mian 2023; Tesfaye et al. 2016; Birdsey & Pan 2015; Calfapietra et al. 2015; Pandey et al. 2019; Zeng et al. 2018, Mo et al. 2023; Do et al. 2023; Mehta & Kaushik 2023; Carnegie et al. 2022).

An increase in forest cover can happen through afforestation, reforestation and natural expansion of forests. Afforestation occurs when trees are planted on land that was not previously forested. The natural expansion of forests refers to an expansion of forest through natural succession onto previously non-forested lands, usually abandoned agricultural land. Reforestation occurs when trees are planted or regenerated on sites that were previously forested. Where part of a forest is cut down but replanted (reforestation), or where the forest grows back on its own within a relatively short period (natural regeneration), there is no change in the forest area. Instead of native plant plantation, exotic plantation and agroforestry practices have become an increasingly important source of timber, firewood, pole and posts. Exotic plantations negatively impact the natural habitat (Rahman 2023d). The study aimed to explore different options for indigenous species plantation.

Methodology

Empirical data was used for this study. The secondary data were reviewed to develop a conceptual framework. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to explore the different options for native plantations based on habitat types and the level of degradation. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Ways of native species plantations

Natural succession in the denuded core zone

The respondents opined that following the human disturbances, the successional species start to establish in the open areas under full sunlight. Eventually, in the absence of further disturbance, they occupy the site through a series of successional stages, leading ultimately to a plant community

comprised of climax species. The denuded areas belonging to the core zone of our natural forests can be reforested through natural succession. However, during the early successional stage, natural regeneration requires protection from further anthropogenic disturbances.

Natural regeneration in the natural habitat

The respondents argued that natural regeneration is an effective means of regenerating the forest when conditions are right. It is usually favourable for the trees suited to the site. Effective natural regeneration from seed depends on seed productivity and dispersal. Alternatively, some species can regenerate from suckers and shoots. Sal (*Shorea robusta*) can effectively regenerate naturally from shoots even after a clearcut harvest. Through natural regeneration, there is a higher probability of developing mixed stands. This may occur even when the original stand is pure. In the core and buffer zones of each forest natural regeneration should be facilitated to maintain the ecological balance and to ensure continuous forest coverage.

Direct (artificial) seeding in the peripheral zone

Direct (artificial) seeding is usually carried out from the ground on sites that have been prepared for seed germination. While it is a more expensive procedure than natural regeneration, there is a greater likelihood of establishing the desired species. Large volumes of seed (5–10 seeds for each seedling) are required for successful regeneration. The respondents stressed direct seeding in the buffer zone and degraded forest areas.

Gap-filling by rare species

The respondents opined that in forests where small-scale disturbances exist, stand dynamics are controlled by the creation of gaps due to single or multiple overstory-tree mortality. Sometimes openings are created due to illegal logging on a small scale. Newly established seedlings or advanced regeneration of rare or endangered species should be recruited in these openings. This will protect the rare and very rare species from extinction as well.

Woodlot plantation in the encroached forest lands

The plantation of hardwood trees to harvest for profits and environmental carbon offset is called woodlot plantation. The respondents argued that invasive species should be avoided for woodlot plantations as they disrupt native biodiversity. Very fast-growing and timbering native species should be planted in the encroached areas.

Riparian plantation

Riparian forests are typically composed of overstorey, understorey and macrophyte species. The respondents stressed planting deep-rooted species (overstorey) for reinforcing riverbanks against mass failure than shallow-rooted groundcover. Trees should be planted around potential slump-block failure planes. However, understorey and groundcover species provide mid- and upper-bank sections with greater

protection from scour. Lower bank sections that tend to remain wet throughout the year are best protected by macrophyte species where they can be established.

Building greenbelts in the coastal areas

The coastal areas of Bangladesh are prone to severe damage from cyclones. It has been proved that dense forest cover along the coastline is an effective protection against the impacts of cyclones. The respondents advocated for planting trees with large canopies, which have deep roots.

The embankment, roadside, and railside plantations

It was recommended that rail-side land, sides of national highways and feeder roads, and river embankments should be planted with native timbering and fuel wood tree species. The roadside trees are pruned twice a year and the branches are used for firewood.

Homestead and institution plantations

The respondents recommended replacing old and unproductive trees in the homesteads with new and high-yielding multipurpose, fruit trees and medicinal plants. The open spaces of schools, colleges, mosques, temples, other institutions, local government offices and cyclone shelters need plantations by multipurpose trees.

Dune plantation

The respondents highlighted planting accredited foreshore and offshore islands for dune stabilising. Screw pine (*Pandanus*) can grow on dunes and has thick 'prop roots' to anchor itself in the loose sand. The abundant mangrove species are suitable for such types of plantations as they have fast-growing roots.

Tanguya plantation

The respondents noted that the *Tanguya* plantation should consist of growing annual crops along with forest trees during the early establishment of forest plantations on the hills. This is a method of establishing crops in temporary combination with forestation. Agricultural cropping ends with the casting of dense lateral shade or closing of the forest canopy. This system can be applied to the afforestation and reforestation programme in the hilly areas.

Urban forestation

Urban forests play an important role in maintaining congenial human habitat in many ways: they filter air, water, and sunlight, and provide shelter and recreational areas for people. They are critical in cooling the urban heat island in peak summer months. In a wider sense, it may include any kind of woody plant vegetation growing in and around human settlements. The respondents stressed planting ornamental plants in urban areas.

Declarations

The author declares that the participants consented to participate in the interviews and and publish this study.

Conflict of Interests: There is no conflict of interests in this manuscript.

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